

Pharmacognostical Investigation and Anti-Bacterial Potential of *Clitoria Ternatea* Linn. (Aparajita) Leaves

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ABSTRACT

Aparajita (*Clitoria ternatea*), commonly known as Asian pigeonwings, blue bellvine, blue pea, butterfly pea, cordofan pea or Darwin pea species belonging to family Fabaceae, which is native to Indonesian Island of Ternate, and commonly cultivated in throughout India. The plant contains Alkaloids, Flavanoids, Steroids, Glycosides, Saponins, Carbohydrates, Tannins, and other phytoconstituents. The traditional uses of Aparajita plant are Antibacterial, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-oxidant, Anti-diabetic etc. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the pharmacognostical parameters, including microscopy, ash values, extractive values, foreign matter determination, and swelling index, along with the antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using the disk diffusion method by assessing the zones of inhibition of Alkaloidal and Flavonoidal fraction of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves. The anti-bacterial activity was performed and zone of inhibition was found 13mm (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and 6mm (*E. coli*).

Keywords: *Clitoria ternatea*, *E.coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Disk-diffusion Method.

INTRODUCTION

Clitoria ternatea (Fabaceae) is known as Butterfly pea, Asian pigeon wings, blue bellvine, cordofan pea and Shankpushpi.[1] The species is indigenous to Southeast Asia and occurs extensively in tropical Asian regions such as India, the Philippines and Madagascar. It is predominantly found in tropical equatorial area, a perennial twinning leguminous herb. The plant attains a length ranging from 0.5 to 3 m. It bears pinnate leaves comprising 5–7 leaflets. The petiole length varies between 1.5 and 3 cm. The plant possesses persistent stipules that are narrowly triangular, subulate in shape, predominantly three-nerved, and measure approximately 1–6 mm in length. Foliolate stipules are 2mm long and shows characteristic elliptical leaflets. *Clitoria ternatea* a perennial climber with white-or blue-coloured flowers [2]. The leaves are both elliptic and obtuse in nature. Being a vine or creeper, it naturally grows well in neutral and moist soil. The fruit from these plants is usually 5 to 7 cm long and possess 6 to 10 seeds within each flat pod. The tender nature of the fruit makes it an edible fruit. The flowers are axillary and solitary.[3]

The plant contains active constituents such as resins, tannins, starch, taraxerone, and taraxerol. It is rich in secondary metabolites, including kaempferol and its glucoside clitorin, taraxerol, and the lactone aparajitin. The seeds specifically contain compounds like hexacosanal, β -sitosterol, and anthoxanthin.[4]

The leaf extract of *Clitoria ternatea* being colourful, after purification is used as a natural colouring agent or natural dye in various food industries. Being a traditional medicinal herb *Clitoria ternatea* is the only species among the Fabaceae family that is bestowed with the presence of cyclotides. Among the plant parts, the roots of *Clitoria ternatea* exhibit the highest cyclotide content. These cyclotides greatly possess antibacterial and immune stimulating activities.[5]

Clitoria ternatea is valued as a medicinal plant, with its roots, leaves, and seeds frequently used in various remedies. The plant shows diuretic and laxative effects.[6] Its seeds are traditionally used to relieve stomach cramps and calm the mind, while the leaves and flowers provide a cooling effect. [7] The whole

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plant extract possesses several medicinal properties, including anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antibacterial, and analgesic activities.[8] It also exhibits antidepressant, anxiolytic, sedative, anticonvulsant, anticancer, and hypoglycemic effects.[9] In traditional Ayurvedic medicine, *Clitoria ternatea* has been used for centuries as a memory enhancer, nootropic, antistress, anxiolytic, antidepressant, anticonvulsant, and sedative agent. [10]

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the pharmacognostical parameters, including microscopy, ash values, extractive values, foreign matter determination, and swelling index, along with the antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using the disk diffusion method by assessing the zones of inhibition of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves.

Fig1- Clitoria ternatea plant

1. MATERIAL AND METHODS:

1.1. Collection and Authentication of plant:

The leaves of *Clitoria ternatea* was collected from Paramedical Campus of Uttar Pradesh university of Medical Sciences (Saifai, Uttar Pradesh) and prepare an herbarium of plant specimen, this plant specimen authenticated by Prof. (Dr.) Rajvir Singh (Head, Department of Botany) K.K.P.G college, Etawah.

1.2. Cleaning and drying of leaves:

The leaves were cleaned under running water for the purpose to remove dust particles and after cleaning of the material next step was drying of plant leaves under the sunlight.

1.3. Organoleptic evaluation:

- To identify the leaves color, odour, and taste with the help of sense organs
- Colour- Evaluated by the help of naked eyes
- Odour- Evaluated by crushing drug in between fingers and smelling
- Taste- Evaluated by the help of tongue tip
- Texture: Evaluated by the help of touching sense rough or smooth
- Shape: Evaluated by the help of naked eyes
- Size: Evaluated by the help of naked eyes

1.4. Microscopical evaluation:

The freshly collected leaves were taken and cleaned by running water and then the cutted in transverse section (T.S) from the midrib of the leaf and then it was exposed to safranin for the dyeing purpose so that leaf can retain the dye in itself and the better evaluation can be performed. Then the transverse section is kept on the stage of microscope and the evaluation is done under 10x power lens.

1.5. Physicochemical evaluation:

The quantitative determination of crushed powder of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves were evaluated as physical constants and chemical properties like foreign matter, ash values, extractive values, moisture content to standardize crude drugs for identity, purity, and quality control.

1.6. Determination of Foreign organic matter

An accurately weighed quantity of 250 g of the plant material was spread evenly in a thin layer on clean filter paper. The sample was examined visually with the aid of a 6x magnifying lens. The identified foreign organic matter was separated, weighed, and its content expressed as a percentage (w/w).

1.7. Determination of moisture content

An accurately measured 5 g portion of the leaves was placed into a pre-weighed porcelain dish. The sample was dried in a hot air oven at 105°C until constant

weight was achieved, as indicated by there was no difference in weight between the two consecutive measurements. LOD was calculated as a percentage w/w with respect to air-dried test material.

1.8. Determination of Ash values

Total ash, acid-insoluble ash and water-soluble ash of the test material were determined following the procedure given in the Indian Pharmacopoeia (1996). The experiment was done in triplicate.

1.8.1. Determination of Total Ash

Total ash was determined by igniting 2 g of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves in a tarred silica crucible at 450 °C until a white residue was obtained. The crucible was cooled in a desiccator and weighed, and ignition was repeated until a constant weight was achieved. The total ash content was calculated as a percentage of the dried leaves using three independent determinations.

Total ash content was calculated by:

$$\text{Total Ash value} = \frac{wt3 - wt2}{wt1} \times 100$$

Wt 1: weight of sample taken

Wt 2: weight of empty crucible

Wt 3: weight of crucible with sample after ignition

1.8.2. Determination of Acid-insoluble Ash

Acid-insoluble ash was determined by boiling the total ash with 25 mL of 2 N hydrochloric acid for 5 minutes, followed by filtration through ashless filter paper (Whatman No. 42). The residue was washed with hot water until neutral, dried, ignited at 450 °C to constant weight, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed. The acid-insoluble ash was calculated with reference to the oven-dried sample.

1.8.3. Determination of Water-soluble ash

Water-soluble ash was determined by boiling the total ash with 25 mL of distilled water for 5 minutes, followed by filtration through ashless filter paper (Whatman No. 42). The insoluble residue was washed with hot water, dried, ignited at 450 °C to constant weight, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed. The

water-soluble ash was calculated by subtracting the weight of the insoluble residue from the total ash and expressing the result as a percentage of the oven-dried sample.

1.9. Determination of extractive values

Alcohol and water-soluble extractive values of the test material were determined by following the procedures given in the Indian Pharmacopoeia (1996). The experiment was done in triplicate.

1.9.1. Alcohol soluble extractive value

The alcohol-soluble extractive value was determined by macerating 5 g of powdered *Clitoria ternatea* leaves with 100 mL of 95% ethanol for 24 h, with intermittent shaking during the first 6 h. After filtration, 25 mL of the filtrate was evaporated to dryness at 105 °C to constant weight. The extractive value was calculated as % w/w of the dried material from the mean of three determinations.

1.9.2. Water-soluble extractive value

The water-soluble extractive value was determined following the same method described above, except that 95% ethanol was replaced with chloroform water. Chloroform water was prepared by diluting 0.25 mL of chloroform with distilled water to make up a final volume of 100 mL.

1.10. Swelling index determination:

2 grams of powdered leaves were placed in a 25 mL stoppered measuring cylinder, and water was added up to the 20 mL mark. The mixture was gently agitated at intervals over a 24-hour period and then allowed to stand. The volume occupied by the swollen material was subsequently recorded.[11]

$$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{\text{Volume of swelled plant material}}{\text{Initially volume of plant material}}$$

1.11. Successive extraction of Plant Material:

After obtaining the coarse powdered form of the leaves was packed into a thimble prepared using filter paper. The thimble was then placed in the Soxhlet

extractor, and extraction was carried out using different solvents in increasing order of polarity.[12]

- **The solvents used in the successive extraction are as following:**

- a. n-Hexane
- b. Toluene
- c. Chloroform
- d. Ethanol
- e. Water

1.12. Phytochemical Screening:

The leaf extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to identify the presence of various classes of phytoconstituents, including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, steroids, triterpenoids, and glycosides. This was determined by performing standard chemical tests for each class of phytoconstituents, and the results are presented in Tables No. 04–07 and Figure No. 03. [13]

2. Quantitative estimation of Alkaloid and Flavonoid content by Gravimetric method:

2.1. Estimation of Alkaloids: Alkaloids were extracted using the hot percolation method in a Soxhlet apparatus maintained at 30°C. 15gm of powdered drug was defatted with n-hexane for 12 h, air-dried, and then basified with ammonia solution. The basified material was extracted with chloroform for 12 h. The chloroform extract was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to transfer alkaloids into the aqueous phase, followed by re-extraction with chloroform. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous salt, evaporated under reduced pressure, and the alkaloid yield was determined.[14]

2.2. Estimation of Flavonoids: 15gm of the leaves was mixed with 100 mL of acidified water (water containing 5 drops of concentrated HCl) and heated on a water bath for 1 h. After cooling, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was transferred to a separating funnel. The filtrate was

successively extracted three times with 25 mL of ethyl acetate, followed by three extractions with 25 mL of n-amyl alcohol. The n-amyl alcohol fraction was collected and concentrated by evaporation on a water bath, and the flavonoid yield was determined.[15]

3. Isolation of Phytoconstituents by Chromatographic method:

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was employed for the preliminary separation and identification of phytoconstituents present in *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. leaves. The analysis was performed on glass TLC plates precoated with silica gel as the stationary phase. Suitable solvent systems were used to achieve effective separation of the constituents. After development, the plates were air-dried and visualized under UV light and by spraying with appropriate detecting reagents. The separated spots were characterized by their R_f values, providing qualitative evidence of bioactive phytochemicals potentially responsible for the antibacterial activity of the leaf extracts [16]

- **Mobile phase for Flavonoid:** Ethyl acetate: Formic acid: Glacial acetic acid: Water (100:11:11:26)
- **Mobile phase for Alkaloid:** Chloroform: Methanol: Dimethylamine (90:10:01)
- **Stationary Phase:** Silica gel 'G'

4. Antibacterial activity of isolated compound fraction:

Preparation of Different Concentration of leaves Extracts and Standardization of Inoculum:

The different concentrations of plant crude extracts were prepared. 100 mg/mL of the extract solution was prepared by dissolving 0.75 g of the extract (Alkaloid and Flavonoid) in 10 mL of methanol in a sterile universal bottle. Two-fold serial dilution was carried out to obtain three concentrations of 50 mg/mL, 25 mg/mL, and 12.5 mg/mL. All of the extracts were stored in the refrigerator at a temperature 4°C before further use. The *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* stock was inoculated on Mueller Hinton Agar

(MHA) using streak plate method and was placed in the incubator for 24 hours at 37°C of obtaining isolated bacterial colonies.

Antibacterial Activity by Disk-diffusion Method:

The antibacterial activity of alkaloid extract, flavonoid extract, and their combined extract from *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. leaves were evaluated using the disk diffusion method. Sterile 6 mm Whatman No. 1 filter paper discs were impregnated with 20 µL of each extract at concentrations of 100, 50, 25, and 12.5 mg/mL. Methanol-impregnated discs served as the negative control, while ampicillin (500 µg/mL) was used as the standard. The impregnated discs were placed on Mueller–Hinton agar plates previously inoculated with *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Plates were allowed to stand at room temperature to facilitate diffusion and then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the zones of inhibition (mm) the result shown in the table no.09 and fig. no. 04[17]

5. Observation and Result:

5.1.Organoleptic evaluation:

- Colour- Green
- Odour- Characteristic odour
- Texture- Smooth
- Taste- Tasteless
- Shape: Ovate to elliptic
- Size:4-08 cm long and 2-5 cm wide

5.2.Microscopy of leaves:

Fig:2 Transverse section of Clitoria ternatea leaves

A: Palisade, **B:** Calcium oxalate crystals, **C:** Cuticle, **D:** Upper epidermis, **E:** Covering trichome, **F:** Xylem, **G:** Phloem, **H:** Lower epidermis,

5.3.Moisture content:The percentage moisture content of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves was found to be **10.6% w/w**.

5.4. Foreign Matter:The percentage of foreign matter in *Clitoria ternatea* leaves was found to be **0.4%w/w**.

5.5.Ash Value:The percentage of the Ash values given in the table below

Table No. 01: Observed value of Ash

Ash value	Observation (% w/w)
Total Ash	7.2
Acid insoluble Ash	1.1
Water soluble Ash	5.3

5.6.Extractive value (percentage yield): The percentage of the extractive values given in the table below.

Table No. 02: Observed Extractive value

Water soluble extractive value	36% w/w
Alcohol soluble extractive value	28% w/w

5.7.Swelling index: The *Clitoria ternatea* leaves swelled to occupy a volume of **2.1 mL**, indicating the presence of mucilage or polysaccharide material.

5.8. Percentage yield by Successive extraction: The percentage of yield of the successive extraction given in the table below

Table No. 03: Observed yield of Successive extraction

Name of solvent	Yield (% w/w)
n-Hexane	0.75
Toluene	1.53
Chloroform	2.63
Ethanol	6.36
Water	6.06

5.9. Chemical tests: All phytochemical screening was carried out using different chemical tests, and the results are presented in the table below

Table No. 04: Chemical test of Alkaloids

Test of Alkaloids	n-Hexane	Toluene	Chloroform	Ethanol	Water
Dragendroff's	-	-	+	+	+
Hager's	-	-	+	+	+
Wagner	-	-	+	+	+

Table No. 05: Chemical test of Flavonoids

Test of Flavonoids	n-Hexane	Toluene	Chloroform	Ethyl acetate	Water
Shinoda	-	-	+	+	+
Alkaline reagent	-	-	+	+	+
Zinc Hydrochloric acid	-	-	+	+	+

Table No. 06: Chemical test of Steroids/ Triterpenoids

Test of Steroids/ Triterpenoids	n-Hexane	Toluene	Chloroform	Ethanol	Water
Salkowski	-	+	+	+	+
Sulphur Powder	-	+	-	+	+

Table No. 07: Chemical test of glycosides

Test of glycosides	n-Hexane	Toluene	Chloroform	Ethanol	Water
General test (A and B)	-	-	+	-	+

(+): Presence, (-): Absence

Fig.3. Chemical test performed in Pharmacognosy lab

5.10. Estimated yield of Alkaloid and Flavonoid: The estimated value of Alkaloid and

Flavonoid by gravimetric method was found to be;

Tab.09: Estimated value of Alkaloid and Flavonoid

% yield of Alkaloid	1.3 % w/w
% yield of Flavonoid	1.7% w/w

6.11. Rf values: The observed Rf value of the extracted phytoconstituents given below

- Rf value of ethyl acetate Flavonoid extract – 0.77
- Rf value of n-amyl alcohol Flavonoid extract –0.68
- Rf value of Alkaloid-0.9

Fig.4. Flavonoid TLC plate Fig.5. Alkaloid TLC plate

6.10. Anti-bacterial activity result: The result of drug susceptibility testing using disc diffusion method for the extracts from plant *Clitoria ternatea* (Aparajita) is as follows:

- **Concentration of disc** – 0.75 mg
- **Media used-** Mueller Hinton Agar

Table No. 09. Antibacterial activity observation

Bacteria	Name of Extract	Zone of inhibition
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Sample 1 - Flavanoids (0.75 mg)	10mm
	Sample 2 - Alkaloids (0.75 mg)	13mm
	Sample 3- Mixture of Sample 1 & 2	12mm
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Sample 1 - Flavanoids (0.75 mg)	6mm
	Sample 2 - Alkaloids (0.75 mg)	6mm
	Sample 3- Mixture of Sample 1 & 2	6mm

Fig.6. *Staphylococcus aureus* plate with inhibition zone **Fig.7. *E. coli* plate with inhibition zone**

CONCLUSION:

The present study establishes pharmacognostical standards for *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. leaves through detailed organoleptic, microscopic, and physicochemical evaluations, ensuring their identity, purity, and quality. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of important bioactive constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, steroids, triterpenoids, and glycosides. Quantitative estimation and TLC profiling confirmed appreciable levels of alkaloids and flavonoids with characteristic Rf values. The antibacterial activity of the isolated fractions demonstrated notable inhibitory effects against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, with greater sensitivity observed in *Staphylococcus aureus*. These findings support the traditional use of *Clitoria ternatea* and indicate its potential as a natural source of antibacterial agents.

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